

The English Speaking Ability of Administrator Officers and Supervisory Officers at the Human Resources Development Agency and the Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province

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Abstract:- English as an International Language which should be mastered by the civil servants, especially Administrator and Supervisory Officers in order to realize SMART State Civil Apparatus 2024. The civil servants are expected to be able to master the information and communication technology, speak foreign languages towards World Class Bureaucracy, also take part in the Industrial Revolution and Society 5.0.

This research is an analysis of the English speaking ability of Administrator and Supervisory Officers, consisted of eighteen officers of the Human Resources Development Agency; and seven officers of the Department of Culture and Tourism. This study aimed to determine the extent to which these officials speak English, including the pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency and understanding of English.

The researcher used a descriptive qualitative approach, namely the results of the research which are then processed and analyzed to draw conclusions. As a result, it was concluded that out of the twenty five officers, none of them were considered to have good command of English in terms of the five aspects of English. There are ten officers were considered to have more than sufficiently proficient in English. There are nine officers who have enough English skills. And there are six officers who were very lacking in all aspects of English skills.

Based on these findings, the researcher recommended some activities to be carried out to improve English proficiency: Forming English Group Discussions, Holding English Days, Forming teams for English Competitions, Demonstrating English Proficiency every Friday, Forming WhatsApp Groups in English, Holding Training classical or non-classical English, and Making regulations so that all Civil Servants are ready to be involved in English language activities for the provincial government level.

Keywords:- Speaking Ability, Performance, Administrator Officer, Supervisor Officer

I. INTRODUCTION

English is an International Language, therefore the ability to speak English is an absolute must for Civil Servants, especially Administrator Officers and Supervisory Officers. It is because having this ability will help Civil Servants to carry out their duties and responsibilities more easily, they will be more confident if they are able to communicate using English, because English is more widely used by the international community. In this digital era, officials are faced with tasks that are closely related to the ability to speak English, especially to translate regulations or rules and to provide informational services to foreign guests who use English.

It really needs competent officials who have good English skills, who will be able to involve themselves and take part in the revolution in the Industrial Revolution 4.0 and Society 5.0. So that, later it will support the achievement of organizational goals that have been implemented previously. All officials as civil servants of the State are expected to master the ability to speak English well to support their duties and realize SMART State Civil apparatus in 2024, among others by having a profile of mastering IT and being able to speak a foreign language (English) towards World Class Bureaucracy in 2025.

Due to the importance of mastering English for administrators and supervisory officers as the State Civil Apparatus when it comes to SMART State Civil Apparatus, the researcher wanted to find out the level of English proficiency of these officials, are they ready to realize SMART State Civil Apparatus 2024 ?

The researcher conducted research at the Human Resources Development Agency, and the Culture and Tourism Office of the Central Kalimantan Province. The two organizations at the Provincial Level were chosen because the researcher was one of the civil servants assigned

at BPSDM Central Kalimantan Province who wanted to know the level of English proficiency of Administrator and supervisor officers at the Department of Culture and Tourism. It is known that the officers of the Department of Culture and Tourism often deal directly with foreign tourists regarding their duties. In order to support the duties of administrator and supervisory officers, the researcher was very interested in conducting research to find out the level of English proficiency of the officers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Alwi (2002), ability is being able of doing something. So that language ability is a person's ability to use the language that is mastered in conveying ideas, including language system, manners, and understanding the sequence of speaking.

Everyone can have abilities, but not everyone can easily have skills. Skills are acquired by habituation and practicing to arrange speech, to prepare techniques for conducting conversation, to capture and respond to listener interest, and to transmit energy in speaking. So what must be prepared for an effective discussion are competency and thorough preparation.

The ability to speak is defined as an expression of opinions, thoughts, or feelings addressed to other people or groups, and is carried out directly or indirectly orally. Speaking is the spearhead of the goal of teaching English. Speaking skill includes the ability to compose sentences as a result from the communication that has been established; so that there are varied behaviors.

Based on the description above, the researcher concluded that speaking ability is a skill aimed to express thoughts, feelings, and opinions to communicate with other people, in this case using English.

In work and bureaucracy, English is also required. Ministries or government agencies often receive important letters or visits from other ministries or state agencies. Of course, it requires responses and feedbacks in English. Thus, English is important for the State Civil Apparatus because of the following reasons:

- Development of educational competencies needs to be carried out in order to increase the knowledge and abilities of Civil Servants through formal education in accordance with laws and regulations, namely the provision of study assignments. Fulfilling the needs of job and career competency standards can be done by giving study assignments. Then the State Civil Apparatus can carry out activities, such as listening, reading and taking references from books in English; then they will communicate or listen to terms in English.
- Competency development can be carried out using classical training routes, such as: training, seminars, courses, regulations, outreach, workshops, semi-workshops, etc.; and non-classical, such as: e-learning,

mentoring in the workplace, distance training, apprenticeships, Civil Servants and private employees exchange, etc.

- The State Civil servants are expected to be able to improve the development of competence to communicate using English, and become one of the efforts to achieve world-class bureaucracy. SMART State Civil Apparatus is the target of the Medium Term Development Plan for the staffing division that must be achieved by the government in 2019. SMART State Civil Apparatus has the following characteristics: mastering information and technology, being able to speak foreign languages, having a global outlook, and being professional.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, researcher used a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2015), descriptive method is a method used to describe or analyze a research result but cannot be used to make broader conclusions. According to Kuncoro (2003), descriptive method includes activities of collecting data to answer questions about the latest status of research subjects. Meanwhile according to Bagdan and Taylor in Moleong (2002), qualitative method is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from the observed people and behavior.

Based on the explanations above, the researcher concluded that the results of this study are processed and analyzed to draw conclusions to produce conclusions that will clarify the description of the object under study.

IV. RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

The Human Resources Development Agency of Central Kalimantan Province has an authority in its area that is assigned to regional heads, in this case the Governor, to help in preparing or improving human resource development, especially civil servants as a support function for government affairs, likewise the Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province. This certainly requires officers, especially Administrator officers and Supervisory officers who are always able to follow the development of science and technology in providing excellent service to service recipients. Thus, it is urgently needed the civil servants who are tough, professional and of course have the ability to speak English related to competence in their respective positions.

In December 2021, according to the list of attendees, there were 18 officials, consisting of: 1 secretary, 3 administrator officers, and 14 supervisory officers. The researcher also conducted interviews with 7 (seven) officials from the Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province. Office service hours are held from Monday to Friday, starts at 08 AM and ends at 03.30 PM. Because the number of infected with COVID-19 started to Decrease, services were adjusted according to the situation and circumstances.

Table 1 The List of Administrator and Supervisor Officers

No.	Name	Age	Education	Position
1	NOR	56	S2	Secretary of Human Resources Development Agency
2	EH	57	S2	Head of Technical Competency Development
3	SY	54	S2	Head of Competency Certification and Institutional Management
4	IS	54	S2	Head of Managerial Competency Development
5	NW	50	S2	Head of Sub Division of Core Competency Development Administrative Positions of Supporting Regional Apparatus
6	IM	53	S2	Head of Sub Division of Competency Certification
7	RF	56	S2	Head of Sub-Division of Institutional Management and Competency Development Staff
8	RA	37	S2	Head of Sub-Division of Program Development
9	YUS	57	S1	Head of Sub-Division of Development of Functional Position Competency
10	TER	57	S1	Head of Sub-Division of Development of Core Competency of Administrator Official of <i>Non-Peldas</i> Mandatory Concurrent Affairs
11	EF	51	S1	Head of Sub-Division of General Competency of Administrator Official
12	RW	43	S1	Head of Sub-Division of Development of Leader Competency and <i>Prajabatan</i>
13	NIN	43	S1	Head of Sub-Division of Regulation of Learning Source and Teamwork
14	MAH	51	S1	Head of Sub-Division of General and Employee Affair
15	EM	42	S1	Head of Sub-Division of of Development of Core Competency of Administrator Official of Mandatory and Alternative Concurrent Affairs
16	ROH	54	S1	Head of Sub-Division of Financial and Asset
17	DUR	44	S1	Head of Sub-Division of of Development of Higher Leader Competency
18	MD	30	S1	Head of Sub-Division of Development of Local Leader Competency
19	RASP	57	High School	Secretary of Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province
20	RM	55	S2	Head of Development of Tourism Destination and Institution
21	MDA	53	S2	Head of History, Preservation of Cultural Heritage and Museums
22	SA	46	S1	Head of Art, Tradition, and Cultural Heritage
23	HAS	56	S1	Head of Tourism Marketing Development
24	SUR	55	S1	Head of UPT. Cultural Park
25	HAR T	54	S1	Head of UPT. Balanga Museum

Based on the data above, there are 11 (eleven) people with a Master's degree (S-2); 13 (thirteen) people with a Bachelor's degree (S-1); and 1 one) with a high school education.

In the assessment, the researcher used 5 (five) aspects that became a reference for evaluating speaking skills or skills, namely grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, understanding and fluency. As for the assessment, the researcher used a score of 1-5 as described in the table below:

Table 2 Speaking Assessment

No.	Aspect	Score	Indicator
1	Pronunciation	5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Easy to understand and master the native accent
		4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Easy to understand and with certain accent
		3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pronunciation needs full attention and causes misunderstanding
		2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Difficult to understand because of the pronunciation problems and repetitions.
		1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Serious problems in conversation and difficult to understand
2	Grammar	5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No or only a few grammatical mistakes/ errors
		4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grammatical errors that not affect to the meaning
		3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Many grammatical errors that affect the meaning
		2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Many grammatical errors that hinder the meaning and frequently re-arrange sentences
		1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical grammatical errors that difficult to understand
		5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vocabulary and expressions like native speakers
		4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sometimes there are incorrect dictions

3	Vocabulary	3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Often there are incorrect dictions that limit the conversation
		2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Incorrect and limited vocabularies that are difficult to understand
		1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Very limited vocabularies so the conversation is not possible
4	Fluency	5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fluency like a native speaker
		4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fluency is slightly disturbed by language problems
		3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fluency is mostly disturbed by language problems
		2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Often there are hesitation and discontinuation because of the language limitations
		1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Speech is intermitten and discontinued so that conversation is impossible
5	Understanding	5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Understanding without difficulties
		4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Understanding in almost everything, but there are repetition in some parts
		3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Understanding in mostly conversation if it is slowed down
		2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Difficult to follow the conversation
		1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not understanding even a simple conversation

The researcher conducted the interviews in December 2021 at the Human Resources Development Agency, and in December 2022 at the Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province with administrators and supervisory officers. After conducting the interviews, the following assessment results were obtained:

Table 3 The Result of the Assessment

No.	Name	ASPEK PENILAIAN SPEAKING				
		Pronun- ciation	Grammar	Voca- bulary	Fluency	Under- standing
1	NOR	4	4	4	4	4
2	EH	4	4	3	3	4
3	SY	4	4	4	4	4
4	IS	4	4	4	4	4
5	NW	3	3	3	3	3
6	IM	4	3	3	4	4
7	RF	3	3	2	3	3
8	RA	4	4	4	4	4
9	YUS	2	2	2	2	3
10	TER	3	2	3	3	3
11	EF	2	2	2	2	2
12	RW	3	2	2	3	3
13	NIN	4	4	4	4	4
14	MAH	3	3	3	3	3
15	EM	4	4	4	4	4
16	ROH	4	4	3	4	4
17	DUR	3	2	3	3	3
18	MD	3	3	3	3	4
19	RASP	4	4	3	3	4
20	RM	4	4	4	4	4
21	MDA	4	4	4	4	4
22	SA	4	4	4	4	4
23	HAS	3	3	3	3	3
24	SUR	4	4	4	4	4
25	HAR T	3	3	3	3	3

Fig 1 Diagram of Research Results Analysis

Based on the values listed above, it shows that the ability of Administrative Officers and Supervisory Officers at the Human Resources Development Agency of Central Kalimantan Province and at the Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province in mastering speaking skills varies. From the aspect of pronunciation, it was found that 56% of officials had the ability in pronunciation that was easy to understand but in it there was still a local accent attached but not too difficult to understand. Meanwhile, the majority still had difficulty in understanding the pronunciation due to several problems including repeated pronunciations, pronouncing several sentences, as well as pronunciations that require the listener to fully concentrate to understand what is being said.

From the grammar assessment, it was found that many officials experienced difficulties in compiling grammar due to several underlying problems, including frequent rearrangements in their sentences, words that did not match meaning and meaning, and the most influential was a lack of vocabulary which ultimately made grammar mistakes and changed the meaning. There were only 20% of officials who had a few errors in grammar but the meaning of the sentence could be conveyed properly.

The next aspect of assessment is the aspect of understanding. It was found that 60% of officials had good understanding by obtaining a score of 4. Only 5% of officials had score of 1 (the lowest). It was found that the official had difficulty in understanding the conversation, even though it had been slowed down and repeated.

Fig 2 Diagram of the Ability Analysis

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is known that there were none of the twenty five administrator and supervisory officers at the Human Resources Development Agency and the Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province who had been interviewed were considered to master English in terms of vocabulary, grammar, fluency, understanding and pronunciation. However, there are ten officers whom the researcher considered to be more than sufficient to master English speaking skills. There are nine officers who were considered to have sufficient English proficiency covering the five aspects. While there are six officers who were very lacking in all aspects of English proficiency.

If the assesment was based on Lambert’s criteria, then no one is included in the category 7-6 (Excellent Level), namely people who have the ability to speak English very proficiently. There are ten officers in category 5 (Good) or people with a good ability to describe and convey ideas to be easily understood. There are eleven officers in category 4 (Satisfied) with speaking skills to share their opinions or basic ideas but also with doubts when expressing their opinions. There are four officers in category 3-1 (improvement-needed) with difficulties in receiving and responding to comments and statements, but with persistence on trying to convey their ideas despite of their limitations/ difficulties.

Based on the conclusion, the researcher is very optimistic that with frequent practice in various ways to speak English, starting from saying greetings when meeting and parting with fellow colleagues in the office to speaking briefly without fear of making mistakes is a good start. Hopefully those who already have the ability to speak English will improve their skills more, especially for Officials who are very lacking to motivate themselves. In the future, all the civil servants could be involved in interesting classical or non-classical activities to improve and practice their English.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

As a result of the research that had been carried out, the researcher made several steps that can be held to motivate all civil servants to participate in training themselves, to sharpen their skills in English, and finally to be involved in supporting the achievement of world-class smart tate Civil Apparatus who have IT skills and master foreign languages in 2024, as well as towards the industrial revolution 4.0. Having a good command of English could help competing in career improvement, have high performance and be ready to face the Community Revolution concept or the 5.0 era.

➤ *The Researcher Recommends Several Activities to the Head of Human Resources Development Agency and to the Department of Culture and Tourism of Central Kalimantan Province, as Follows:*

- Forming an English Group Discussion as a forum for Administrator Officers and Supervisory Officers as well as all other civil servants to improve their English language skills. A weekly discussion for 60 minutes could be held to discuss some issues, simple and complex ones
- Holding English Day every Friday. This aims to familiarize all Civil Servants and Honorary Employees to use English from very simple things, for example: greeting (Greeting) colleagues to each other. With this activity it is hoped that all employees will become accustomed to speaking English during working hours.
- Forming a team to hold English competition activities, such as: story-telling, speech, singing English songs, etc. This activity can be held annually on certain commemorations, such as the Republic of Indonesia's Independence Day by providing interesting prizes to motivate employees who have the ability to speak English.
- Provide opportunities for all employees to show their English skills, both individually and in groups after Friday morning workout; for example: singing English songs, introducing themselves and families in English, having simple English conversations with colleagues, telling stories, etc.
- Forming a special WhatsApp group to practice English skills in written language which is very useful for all employees. A prize for the most active member in certain time (2 weeks or a month) can be given as a reward/appreciation.
- Requiring to speak English on a certain day to civil servants of all Regional Apparatus Organization of the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government by making Regulations or Circulars.
- Conducting English language training for civil servants of the Provincial Government in a classical or non-classical activities regularly.

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